

SUPERSATURATION LIMITS OF SOLUTIONS. PART II

BY RAMA GOPAL

In continuation with the previous work a few more salts have been studied. The results obtained appear to show that $\lambda(T_s - T)$ is, in general, proportional to σV_M , the terms used have their usual significance. In particular cases where σV_M values are not very different, $\lambda(T_s - T)$ is approximately a constant.

A new method for calculating the radius r , of the stable crystal nucleus at the first temperature of spontaneous crystallisation under specified conditions, has been developed and it is shown that r is of the order of 10^{-6} cm. Further r is found to vary hyperbolically with the degree of supersaturation.

The limits of supersaturation $T_s - T$ for halides and nitrates of K, Rb, and Cs have been calculated from the formula $T_s - T = 13\sigma V_M/\lambda$ and it is pointed out that the results obtained are similar to the conclusion arrived at by Jones.

In a previous communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 183) it has been shown that $\lambda(T_s - T)$, where T_s denotes the saturation temperature, T , the temperature of first spontaneous crystallisation and λ , the heat of solution, is nearly a constant in the case of a number of monovalent salts of sodium and potassium and that its value is approximately 80,000 cal. under conditions specified in the communication. This work has been extended and a number of other substances have been investigated. Experimental arrangements are the same as before and the results obtained are given in Table I.

TABLE I

K_2SO_4			$K_2Cr_2O_7$			$K_3Fe(CN)_6$		
T_s	T	$T_s - T$	T_s	T	$T_s - T$	T_s	T	$T_s - T$
48	20'4, —, —	27'6	40	27'0, 25'2, 23'0	13'0	35	24'0, 23'2, 20'0*	11'0
50	25'0, 26'8, 26'0	25'0	45	32'2, 30'0, 30'0*	12'8	40	28'2, 25'0, 27'6	11'8
55	29'4, 28'2, 28'0	24'6	50	36'8, 36'4, 32'4	13'2	45	32'6, 33'6, 32'0	12'4
58	30'2, —, —	27'8	55	41'6, 40'2, 31'0	13'4	50	37'4, 36'2, 37'0	12'6
60	32'8, 32'4, 32'6	27'2	60	46'4, 43'2, 40'2	13'6	55	43'4, 42'0, 41'6	12'6
63	36'0, 36'2, 35'8	27'0	65	52'4, 50'4, 35'8	12'6	60	47'8, 43'4, 48'0	12'2
65	37'6, 38'0, 36'8	27'4	70	56'2, 54'2, 46'2	13'8	65	52'0, 51'4, 45'2	12'6
70	43'0, 42'8, 42'0	27'0	75	62'0, 59'2, 52'4	13'0			
Approx. mean = 27'0			Approx. mean = 13'2			Approx. mean = 12'0		
$K_4Fe(CN)_6$			K_2CrO_4 **			$HgCl_2$		
T_s	T	$T_s - T$	T_s	T	$T_s - T$	T_s	T	$T_s - T_s$
50	25'2, 22'0, 23'8	24'8(?)	70	36'2	33'8	50	26'8, —, —	23'2
55	30'0, 26'4, 21'0*	25'0(?)	65	32'4	32'6	55	31'2, 31'0, 25'0	23'8
60	37'8, 35'0, 32'8	22'8(?)	60	27'0	33'0	60	35'2, 34'0, 34'2	24'8
65	46'0, 40'2, 39'0	19'0				65	41'0, 39'8, 40'4	24'0
70	51'4, 52'4, 42'8	18'6			33'0	70	43'0, 35'0, —	27'0
75	55'4, 53'2, 49'6	19'6				80	54'0, 53'8, 53'8	26'0
Approx. mean = 18'4			Ba(NO ₃) ₂ $T_s - T$ is about 18'5' (vide previous paper)			Approx. mean = 25'0		

* Solutions did not crystallise down to these temperatures.

** Dissolution of the substance is extremely slow and hence this operation takes a very long time. Consequently the data are not very reliable as the continuous heating might vitiate the limits. Besides the slow dissolution makes a more detailed investigation of the substance almost impossible.

Evidently from Table I, $T_s - T$ is almost a constant for the same substance irrespective of the value of T_s provided T is taken as the temperature of first spontaneous crystallisation. On subsequent heatings to redissolve the crystals, it is found that, in general, T goes on decreasing thereby $T_s - T$ is increased. This phenomenon is a very general one and will receive full attention in a separate communication. The values of λ ($T_s - T$) vary considerably from substance to substance as is clear from Table II.

TABLE II

Salt.	$-\lambda$ in cal.	$T_s - T$.	$\lambda^* (T_s - T)$.
HgCl ₂	3300	25.0	82500
K ₂ SO ₄	6380	27.0	176860
K ₂ CrO ₄	5230	33.0	172790
Ba(NO ₃) ₂	9400	18.5	173900
K ₃ Fe(CN) ₆	14400	12.0	172800
K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	16700	13.5	225450
K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆	16900	20.0	338000

TABLE III

Salt.	$\lambda (T_s - T)$.	$**\sigma V_M$.	$\frac{\lambda (T_s - T)}{\sigma V_M}$.
KCl	78897	5693	13.9
KBr	82804	6019	13.7
KI	79205	6707	11.9
KNO ₃	114400	6555	17.4 (?)
NaNO ₃	65390	4813	13.6
NaCl	62220	4449	13.9
K ₂ SO ₄	171860	14040	12.3
K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	225450	19166	11.8

The significance of the variation in the value of λ ($T_s - T$) is discussed below.

Relation between λ ($T_s - T$) and σV_M .—In the derivation of the relationship

$$\lambda (T_s - T) = 2\sigma V_M \times \frac{T_s}{r},$$

it was assumed that if T_s in the case of similar substances were almost a constant, then $\lambda(T_s - T)$ should vary directly as σV_M . As the values of σ for all the substances investigated are not known, it is not possible to verify the generality of the latter statement; but from the scanty figures which are available it may be concluded that surface energy and molecular volume, most probably, play a very important rôle in the spontaneous crystallisation of these substances (*vide* Table III).

The last column of Table III shows clearly that $\lambda(T_s - T)$ is approximately proportional to the product σV_M . Hence it appears to be fairly justified to assume that the factor T_s/r is approximately constant for substances mentioned in Table III. In other words, the spontaneous crystallisation of the aqueous solutions of any of these salts depends to a great extent on its heat of solution λ , its specific surface energy, σ and its molecular volume V_M under identical conditions. In short the experimental results obtained hitherto lead to the following conclusions:—

(1) $\lambda (T_s - T)$ is, in general, proportional to σV_M .

(2) For substances whose σV_M values are approximately equal, the limit of supersaturation $T_s - T$ varies inversely as the molecular heat of solution λ .

A New Method for Calculating the Value of r , the Radius of the Stable Crystal Nucleus at the Temperature of its Spontaneous Crystallisation.—Making use of the relationship

$$\frac{\lambda(T_s - T)}{\sigma V_M} = 13.0, \text{ an estimate of the size of the stable crystal nucleus can be made with the help}$$

of the equation $\lambda(T_s - T) = 2\sigma V_M T_s/r$ in the following way:—

* Only positive numerical value of λ should be considered (see author's previous communication).

** The value of σ used is of the melt of the substance concerned and is the interpolated (to 30°) value from the experimental data supplied by Jaeger (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1917, 101, 185).

$$\lambda(T_s - T)J = 2\sigma V_n T_s / r \quad (\lambda \text{ converted into ergs})$$

or

$$r = \frac{2\sigma V_n}{\lambda(T_s - T)J} T_s \quad \dots (1)$$

Substituting 13.0 for $\frac{\lambda(T_s - T)}{\sigma V_n}$ in (1) we get,

$$r = \frac{2}{13 \times 4.2 \times 10^7} T_s = 0.036 \times 10^{-7} T_s \text{ cm.} \quad \dots (2)$$

From this equation the values of r for different values of T_s have been calculated and are given in Table IV.

TABLE IV

T_s in °C	...	10°	20°	30°	40°	50°
$r \times 10^6$ cm.	...	1.0	1.03	1.08	1.10	1.13

From Table IV it appears that the size of the stable crystal nucleus is about 100 times

FIG. 1

the molecular dimensions. Ostwald considered that the particles containing less than 10^8 to 10^{12} atoms or molecules are incapable of inducing crystallisation in supersaturated solutions. Assuming the crystal nucleus to be spherical, its radius in aqueous solutions of KCl at the lower limit considered by Ostwald amounts to 1.2×10^{-5} cm. and 2.5×10^{-4} cm. respectively which is 10 to 100 times as large as those given above. However, the values obtained in this paper are supported by the researches of a number of workers. McIntosh (*Trans. Roy. Soc. Canada*, 1819, 13, iii, 265) has shown that in salol the necessary mass to cause crystallisation does not exceed 4×10^{-15} g., which gives a particle of radius less 1×10^{-5} cm. Tammann and Gronow (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1931, 200, 57) consider that the active particle is generally of a

size containing atoms and molecules 10^7 times less than that suggested by Ostwald. Hence radii of such particles at the two limits considered by Ostwald are 1.2×10^{-6} cm. and 5.5×10^{-8} cm., the former of which agrees with the results obtained here. Hamburger (*Chem. Weekblad.*, 1938, 35, 886) considered the size of the active nucleus for high supersaturation of poorly soluble substances to be made of only a few atoms and molecules specially under the influence of the absorptive forces of the walls of the container. On the other hand Hinshelwood and Hartley (*Phil. Mag.*, 1922, 43, 78) have calculated the radius of the stable crystal nucleus for a few organic melts by the application of the Nernst Heat Theorem (a modification of the Ostwald's method). The value obtained by them for undercooled *p*-toluidine melt is of the order of 10^{-8} cm. when the value of σ used is 10^3 ergs. per sq. cm. It appears that

the value of σ used is too high. According to Jaeger (*loc. cit.*) σ for *o*-toluidine is about 40 ergs per sq. cm. at 25°. There is no reason to suppose that it will rise to 1000 ergs in its *para*-form. Hence taking σ for *o*-toluidine to be about 50 ergs (its density being a little higher than the *o*-form its σ should be a little greater) the radius becomes about 1.1×10^{-6} cm. at 25°, a value quite in agreement with that obtained in this investigation. It appears therefore to be fairly certain that the radius of the active crystal nucleus is of the order of 10^{-6} cm. The nucleus of a radius 10^{-5} cm. appears to be too large and it will act as an active centre even in the immediate neighbourhood of the saturation temperature as will be clear from Fig. 1.

Some General Results on Supersaturation

The results arrived at thus far lead to the following important conclusions :—

The radius r of the stable crystal nucleus at any temperature T , in an aqueous solution saturated at T_s is, in general, given by the expression

$$r = 2\sigma V_M T_s / \lambda (T_s - T) J \quad \dots (3)$$

For a number of substances $\frac{\lambda(T_s - T)}{\sigma V_M}$ values are approximately equal under specified conditions (Table IV), hence r is proportional to T_s in these cases. The value of r under these conditions is of the order of 10^{-6} cm. Further from (3) it is clear that r is proportional to $T_s / (T_s - T)$ for any particular solute as now σ , V_M and λ are constants. Consequently different solutions (T_s varies) of the same substance will have different values of r at the same temperature (T is kept constant).

Equation (3) can be written as

$$r (T_s - T) = 2 \sigma V_M T_s / \lambda J \quad \dots (4)$$

If for any particular solute T_s is kept constant (4) reduces to

$$r (T_s - T) = \text{a constant.} \quad \dots (5)$$

The equation (5) shows that r varies hyperbolically with the degree of supersaturation $T_s - T$. For a solution of KCl saturated at $T_s = 300^\circ\text{K}$ (5) becomes

$$r(T_s - T) = 2 \times 5693 \times 300 / 4046 \times 4.2 \times 10^7 = 1.8 \times 10^{-5} \quad \dots (6)$$

Plotting r against $T_s - T$ a rectangular hyperbola is obtained as shown in Fig. 1.

It is clear that in the beginning, inspite of large reduction in the value of r from $r = \infty$ to $r = 10^{-5}$ cm., the degree of supersaturation is so small that the formation of an active crystal nucleus is very improbable. However, the curve takes a very sharp bend in the neighbourhood of $r = 10^{-6}$ cm. and now $T_s - T$ rapidly increases with slight variations in r . Hence formation of stable crystal nucleus leading to spontaneous crystallisation is very probable within this region. The curve gives a satisfactory explanation of the hyperbolic nature of the energy- $(T_s - T)$ diagrams obtained by Young and others (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 33, 158) in a number of cases. A very large value of r in the immediate neighbourhood of T_s requires an impact of large energy content for the formation of the stable crystal nucleus which may start crystallisation whereas reverse will be the case when the degree of supersaturation is very large.

The relationship $\lambda(T_s - T) = \text{a constant}$ has been employed with success in supersaturated solutions of KClO_4 , whose data for $T_s - T$ under given conditions have already been published (*loc. cit.*). Considering KClO_4 to belong to the category of other monovalent salts of potassium its limit of supersaturation $T_s - T$ should be about 80000/12100 or 6.6 degrees. Some experiments with sealed solutions of KClO_4 were performed using solubilities given in Comey and Hahns' "Dictionary of Solubilities etc." The temperature of spontaneous crystallisation appeared to be indefinite and $T_s - T$ was always less than 4°. It was therefore suspected that the solubility data given in this book might be erroneous. Bornstein Tables (recent editions) were then consulted and it was found that recently determined solubilities were quite different from the older values. Experiment with these solubility figures yielded results quite in agreement with the expected value of $T_s - T$ for KClO_4 .

With this successful application and utility of the result $\lambda(T_s - T) = \text{a constant}$ a little hypothetical indulgence may be permitted. For any theoretical prediction, one may consider solutions with relatively smaller viscosities and therefore a free movement of the crystal forming units is possible in these solutions. For highly viscous solutions nothing can be foretold as the formation of the crystal nuclei is very uncertain and improbable, and their growth is very slow due to hindrance in the free movement of the units. Again the rate of cooling of the solution should be neither too rapid nor too slow. The former does not give time enough for the crystal nucleus to grow and further at a lower temperature which is quickly attained increase in viscosity and decrease in molecular motion (*cf.* Freundlich, "Colloid and Capillary Chemistry", 1922, p. 319) hinder the formation of the crystal nucleus, while the latter condition gives too much time, and, probability for crystalline nucleus to be formed above the normal value of T is very great and this will naturally favour a lower supersaturation than predicted by the above relationship. As the aqueous solutions of the salts of K, Rb and Cs of the common inorganic acids will be very suitable for treatment in this manner, these will be considered here. Here again it is assumed that T_s/r is approximately the same in all these cases and hence $T_s - T = 13 \sigma V_M / \lambda$.

Table V gives the values of supersaturation limits $T_s - T$ for aqueous solutions of halides and nitrates of K, Rb and Cs calculated from the above formula. Experimental values for K salts are given in a previous communication (*loc. cit.*). In these calculations the values of λ at high dilutions and specific surface energy values σ intrapolated to 30° from the experimental data of Jaeger for melts of these substances, have been employed in all these cases. Naturally much reliance and accuracy should not be expected and values must be treated as highly approximate figures. Nevertheless they give an idea of the extent of supersaturation obtainable in these solutions.

TABLE V

Supersaturation limits of some aqueous solutions calculated from the formula

$$T_s - T = 13 \sigma V_M / \lambda$$

Cation	Anion															
	Cl ⁻				Br ⁻				I ⁻				NO ₃ ⁻			
	λ	σ	σV_M	$T_s - T$	λ	σ	σV_M	$T_s - T$	λ	σ	σV_M	$T_s - T$	λ	σ	σV_M	$T_s - T$
K ⁺	4046	151	5693	18.3*	5080	139	6019	15.4*	5110	127	6707	16.9*	8520	136	6550	9.6*
Rb ⁺	4500	146	6132	17.8	5060	138	6979	15.2	6500	126	7862	15.6	—	129	8525	—
Cs ⁺	4750	136	5712	15.6	6300	128	6144	12.6	8104	106	6116	9.6	—	120	6240	—

* Experimental values in the above order are 19.5, 16.3, 15.5 and 13.0.

It appears from Table V that $T_s - T$, in general, is in a decreasing order of K, Rb and Cs. This is in agreement with the conclusion arrived at by Jones (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 1739), who found that the degrees of supersaturations of KNO_3 , $RbNO_3$ and $CsNO_3$, in equally rocked solutions are 4° , 1° and 0° respectively. Unfortunately the lack of data for λ of these salts does not permit verification of these results but from an analogy with the halides of these metals the results appear to be in general agreement. Further, the degrees of supersaturation vary roughly as the inverse of the respective molecular weight, a conclusion arrived at by Jones.

The values of the limits of supersaturation given in Table V for Rb and Cs salts may be a little too high. A lower hydration and higher ionic volume of these ions as compared with that of K^+ may favour a lower supersaturation as both these properties offer better chances of forming stable crystal nuclei at lower degrees of supersaturation. Further the salts may be expected to have an almost constant $T_s - T$, i.e., it is almost independent of the amount of heating as in the case of many K salts.

Author's best thanks are due to Dr. A. C. Chatterji for guidance and to the Lucknow University for the grant of a research fellowship.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY.

Received November 3, 1943.